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Simple, fast and accurate method for detection of human mycotic keratitis

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The current study mainly designed for rapid detection of mycotic keratitis in patients. Ordinary culturing of infection swap was time consuming. SCAR-PCR-based DNA amplification was conducted by using a highly specific primer pairing for detection of fungal chitin synthase gene conserved region, for all samples expected to be infected with fungi; specially by using the primer pairing probability (Forward primer: 5'- TAC AAG CTT ACT ATG TAT AAT GAG GAT -3' + Reverse primer: 5'- TTA CTC GAG CTT ATA CTC AAA ATT TTG -3'). The obtained results confirmed that this method gave more accurate, time-saving, as positive visualization of fungal genome was achieved only after 1 day of work, while ordinary cultures consumed about 4 to 14 days to visualize the fungal growth.

Introduction

Mycotic keratitis is considered to be a resistant corneal ulcer, which possesses aggressive fungal growth, and becomes not responding to conventional treatments for at least one week, or more, and even becomes worse due to continued fungal growth, toxification of cornea by drugs and fungal secretions (Tanure *et al.*, 2000). Anatomically, fungal infections are commonly established within collagen-bound lamellae of stromal tissue, which is the mediate layer occupying the major area of human cornea. However, fungal growth rarely invades deeper areas of eye ball, it may reach the anterior chamber behind the cornea in some aggressive cases; but all fungal infections possess non-transparent fungal elements, such as hyphae, spores, or even unicellular forms; that cause a dramatic visual impairment (Sandhu and Rattan, 1981). The severity of corneal fungal infections depends on the complete destruction of loosen stromal layer by the proliferation of large-sized hyphae of filamentous fungi, or highly populated cells of yeast forms within the non-bound stromal lamellae (Cristol *et al.*, 1996). Physiologically, fungal infections can be established due to the high capacity of different fungal elements for adhesion to the host cells, and aided by fungal enzymes production for destroying the host anatomical defense mechanisms, and host surface barriers. Adhesion of fungal elements to the corneal surface depends on both host and pathogen factors, beside the surrounding circumstances (Chander and Sharma, 2004).

Bharathi *et al.* (2003) reviewed many cases of individual fungal representation, and stated that *Arthrotrichum*, *Helminthosporium*, *Cladosporium*, *Neosartorya*, *Colletotrichum*, and *Phaeotrichoconis* were only isolated for a few times from about 1 to 3 cases of corneal ulcers. A local study on mycotic keratitis in Egypt recorded the isolation of 4 different fungal species for the first time from corneal infections, namely *Athelia rolfsii*, *Trimmatostroma salicis*, *Stachybotrys chartarum*, and *Mortierella horticola* (Mahmoud *et al.*, 2004). *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Penicillium lanosum* were the most common isolates from corneal ulcers, as they were represented in 19, 11, and 9 cases respectively (Table 1). Mycotic keratitis possesses a great problem of clinical misdiagnosis, and late laboratory detection, that may refer to several clinical, and laboratory factors. Ophthalmology practice in developing countries revealed that before reaching a specialist, patients with mycotic keratitis have already received a variety of treatments, including antibacterial, antiviral, steroid and even antifungal agents in various combinations; that leads to great modifications for the clinical picture of mycotic keratitis to a variable extent, making the correct diagnosis very difficult (Thomas, 2003). Culture techniques are widely used in laboratory diagnosis, that confirm the fungal growth in the infected sample, and also provide antifungal sensitivity for a conventional treatment. The majority of fungal isolates can give observable growth within 48-96 hours, but at least 25% of corneal scraps require an incubation period of up to 3 weeks for appearance of fungal growth (Ferrer *et al.*, 2001).

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) has been emerged as a new promising tool, which has been shown to be useful for the culture-independent diagnosis of various microbial infections, including mycosis. Most available PCR strategies depend on limited commercially available primers. To achieve accurate detection of fungal genome with high specificity than other microbial genomes, there is a need to design fungal specific primers, which anneal only with fungal DNA, but not with other microbial DNA of either pathogenic or normal microfloral origin. Many distinct characters of fungi, such as chitin of cell wall, ergosterol of cell membrane, fungal ribosomal RNA of both large subunit (28s rRNA) and small subunit (18s rRNA), have a specific identity for their genetic origin in the fungal genome. These unique DNA sequences can be easily used to design specific primers able to recognize a key sequence of fungal DNA, to amplify the fungal genome even in very small amounts of corneal scraps expected to include a fungal infection. A trial to diagnose candidiasis succeeded to use a new PCR technique in early detection of the fungal growth in 3 different immunocompromised patients (Hui *et al.*, 2000). The early detection of fungal elements in blood stream of aspergillosis patients, using PCR technique was also advocated by Hue *et al.* (1999).

Materials and methods

Two samples were achieved from each patient; the first sample was dropped in 0.5 ml sterile saline solution, and frozen at -20°C for further DNA analytical work. The other sample was introduced to perform the ordinary culture for more investigations. This parallel sampling was adopted to achieve the aim of the present study. All samples were collected under fully sterilized conditions. Then C-streaks were made on Sabouraud's dextrose agar culture plates to distinguish microbial growth coming from corneal scraping, and other plate contaminants (Margo and Brinser, 1987). All plates were incubated at 27°C for 4 to 21 days. Fungal colonies were subcultured for purification, and identification on the same medium under the

same incubation conditions. All purified fungal plates were photographed by instant camera (Sony Cybershot - DCR - 480E, Japan); then morphologically, and microscopically examined to be identified according to Raper and Thom (1949); Gilman (1959); Raper and Fennel (1965); Raper *et al.* (1968); Booth (1971); Ellis (1971) and Moubasher (1993).

The chitin synthase genes are unique constituents in fungal genome, and can be used as very distinct tools for recognition of fungi in different unknown medical samples expected to be infected with fungi. Chua *et al.* (1994) recorded five different sequences of chitin synthase genes in five different fungal taxonomic criteria in the gene bank (oomycetes, zygomycetes, ascomycetes, basidiomycetes, and deuteromycetes), possessing a fragment of about 420 bp length with a conserved gene region with a common, and unique sequence, that can be generalized for all the recorded fungal taxa at 5'-3' direction as follows: ATG AAA AGC ACC CTA TAT GGG GAA AAG ACA GCT GGC AGA AAG TGG TGG TGG TCA TTG TAT GCG TGA GTC GAC TGA AAA TGA ACG CTC GAA CGC GGC GTG TGC TTG CTG CTA TGG GCA TAT ACC AGG AAG GTG TTG GGA AAA ACA CTG TGC AAG GGG CCC CTG TGG AAG CCC ACA TGT ACG AAT ATA CAA CTC AAA TTT CAA TTG ACC CGT CCC TCA AGT TCC GCA GTG CGG AGC GCG GAA TTG TCC CTG TAC AGG TAC TGC TTT GTA TCA AGG AGC ATA ACA AGA AGA AAA TCA ATT CTC ACC GGT GGG CTT TCA ATG CAT TTG GTC CTC TTC TGC AGC CTA ACG TCT GCA TGC TTC TCG ATG TGG GTA CCA TGC CTA CGG CTC GCA GTA AAA ATC GAC TTT GGG AGG CGT TTG ACC GCG TAA.

Four different degenerate primers were designed by Chen *et al.* (1992) to be used in the amplification of the common sequence region of chitin synthesis; two forward primers could be used for amplification of 3' – 5' strand of tested DNA samples with the following sequences: Primer-1= 5'- TAC AAG CTT ACT ATG TAT AAT GAG GAT -3', and Primer-2= 5'- TAC AAG CTT ACG ATG TAC AAC GAA GAC -3'. The other two reverse primers could be used for the amplification of 5'-3' anti-sense strand of the same tested DNA samples with the following sequences: Primer-3= 5'- TTA CTC GAG TTT GTA TTC GAA GTT CTG -3', and Primer-4= 5'- TTA CTC GAG CTT ATA CTC AAA ATT TTG -3'. In the present study, these primers could be used as double paired primers for the amplification of the chitin synthase conserved gene region to delimit the range of long DNA fragment targets in the unknown samples of human keratitis as a strategy for early diagnosis of mycotic corneal ulcers for both high accuracy, and rapid detection of fungal infections in uncultured corneal scraps in a comparison with ordinary fungal cultures, that possess long term incubation, and non-representative sampling techniques. Four primers (forward, and reverse with 2 probable sequences for each) were ordered in separate formulations as a product of BioBrick primers (Invitrogen, USA), and stored at -20°C.

A modification of the original CTAB (Cetyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide) procedure of DNA isolation from fresh tissues (Doyle and Doyle, 1990) was adopted for revealing a purified DNA sample from human corneal scraps convenient for use in next PCR analysis techniques, with accurate results. Control samples were treated with all the previously explained DNA extraction, and purification steps to be used in a comparison to qualify the efficiency of the DNA analysis protocols of unknown DNA samples from the previously stored corneal scraps for the specific detection of fungal genome in unknown human infection samples. These control samples included tap water, standard bacterial sample

(*Escherichia coli*, authenticated by bacteriology Research unit, Botany Department, Faculty of Science, Tanta University), and finally, known fungal sample (*Fusarium moniliforme*, authenticated by Mycology Research Unit, Botany Department, Faculty of Science, Tanta University). All purified DNA control samples were stored at -20°C to be used in further DNA analysis.

For each one of control purified DNA samples (tap water, standard bacteria and standard fungus genomes), and unknown purified DNA samples (from diseased corneal scraps); four PCR runs were performed with the different primer pairing probabilities ($P_a = P.1+P.3$, $P_b = P.1+P.4$; $P_c = P.2+P.3$, and $P_d = P.2+P.4$) for achieving acute, and highly sensitive amplification of even rarely presented fungal DNA target in very small or diluted samples. These 4 PCR runs (one for each probability for the same sample) ensure the desired early diagnosis of fungal infections to avoid misdiagnosis problems of human mycotic keratitis according to a procedure modified from Mullis *et al.* (1988). Denaturation step was the first regular cycling event, and consisted of heating the reaction mixture to 95°C for 30 sec.; Annealing step was the second regular cycling event, and consisted of lowering the reaction temperature to 45°C for 30 sec.; Extension (elongation) step was the third regular cycling event, and consisted of arising the reaction temperature to 72°C for 120 sec. The last three regular cycling events were repeated for 45 times to get an efficient DNA amplification, and to ensure the amplification of target DNA even in more diluted or very small samples. After the last denaturation step, the final elongation step was performed for a single time occasionally at 72°C for 10 min. to ensure that any remaining target single-stranded DNA was fully extended. Final hold step was carried out by cooling the reaction mixture to 4°C for short period storage, or frozen at -20°C for long period storage till further analysis protocols.

Each PCR product sample was warmed to room temperature, and applied for electrophoresis on agarose gel according to a procedure modified from that adopted by Williams *et al.* (1990) for documentation of successful specific amplification of fungal chitin synthase common sequence gene region, and to compare the efficiency of different specific primer pairing probabilities in detection, and amplification of target DNA fragments, referring to control samples. The sizes of amplified DNA fragments were determined by comparison with the used standard DNA ladder; also unknown samples were compared with control to distinguish the sensitivity of the used primers to detect the fungal chitin synthase gene common sequence in both fungal, and non-fungal samples. In addition, all samples were compared for different primer pairing probabilities to elucidate their efficiency to be used in a new strategy in early detection of fungal genome in all the tested samples with avoidance of any missed specific fungal DNA detection, even in very small amounts.

Results and Discussion

The present survey covered a total of 50 cases of human mycotic corneal ulcers. Table (1) illustrates the fungal species isolated from mycotic corneal ulcers during the year of survey (2008). The data revealed that *Aspergillus flavus* was the most common isolate (19 cases = 38% out of total mycotic ulcers) among all identified isolates, followed by *Aspergillus niger* (12 cases = 24% out of total mycotic ulcers), then *Penicillium lanosum* (9 cases = 18% out of total mycotic ulcers). *Fusarium moniliforme* was isolated from 6 cases (= 12% out of total mycotic ulcers), while two other fungal species were rarely represented among the

studied ulcers, namely *Mucor fuscus*, and *Cladosporium sphaerospermum* (only 2 cases for each isolate). It was observed that ordinary culture techniques were highly time-consuming strategies, as most of corneal scraps reveal the fungal growth after incubation period of about 4 to 14 days. Growth of *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Mucor fuscus* appeared on culture plates after 4 days of incubation, as shown in table (1); also the first growth on culture plates of *Penicillium lanosum*, and *Fusarium moniliforme* appeared after 9 days of incubation. On the other hand, the incubation period of *Cladosporium sphaerospermum* reached 14 days to approach an observable growth on culture plates. It was very important to study more easy, rapid, and reliable method for early detection, and early treatment of mycotic keratitis.

Specific amplification of fungal genome in each of the diseased corneal samples was carried out with different 4 primer pairing probabilities, using fungal chitin synthase gene-specific primers ($P_a = P.1+P.3$, $P_b = P.1+P.4$; $P_c = P.2+P.3$, and $P_d = P.2+P.4$), that were found to be more faster, and reliable method than ordinary cultures, revealing results after only one day of sample dealing through a SCAR-PCR strategy (sequence characterized amplified region polymerase chain reaction), which was adopted in the present study, (Table 2). PCR-amplified products were documented on agarose gel electrophoresis, and photographed in a comparison with different control samples, such as tap water, standard bacterial isolate, and standard fungal isolate to evaluate the reaction specificity (Table 2).

This highly advanced, and specific SCAR-PCR technique lowered the time consumption from 4-14 days for ordinary cultures to only one day for early detection of fungal infections of human cornea. It elucidated the presence of fungal infection through detection of fungal genome in the unknown samples with highly accurate result, and highly distinct specificity. For standardization of specific PCR-amplification, and visualization of fungal DNA, there was complete absence of electrophoresis bands in tap water, and bacterial samples, acting as non-mycotic negative controls. In the meantime, positive banding was observed at the size of 400 bp in a comparison with a standard DNA marker for the standard fungal sample. Average band size of 380-420 bp was recorded for all the unknown patient samples of the studied 50 cases, which were clinically diagnosed as mycotic keratitis, and confirmed by culture results. The average band size of visualized PCR-products was summarized into 24 cases for the band size of 400 bp, and 14 cases for the band size of 380 bp, while the band size of 420 bp was recorded for 12 cases out of all the studied diseased samples (Tables 2, and 3; and figure 1).

Tables (3 and 4), and figure (1) illustrate a detailed study for the visualization of SCAR-PCR-products of the specific fungal DNA detection by specific amplification of chitin synthase conserved gene region for all unknown corneal samples expected to possess mycotic infections with each one of the different primer pairing probabilities. These probabilities elucidated the efficacy of the adopted technique in the detection of fungal genome even in very small amounts of samples. This strategy could help to compare the efficacy for each one of the pairing probabilities to achieve high density bands (high concentration of amplified DNA fragments), and clear visualization of PCR-products of the desired DNA target.

Table (4), and figure (1) revealed that the first primer probability (P_a) gave positive amplification of target fungal DNA fragments in all the studied 50 cases with low density bands in 15 cases, moderate density bands in 11 cases, and high density cases in 24 cases. It was clear that the second primer pairing probability P_b

was recorded to be the highest incidence of high density bands among all studied probabilities, as it possessed high density bands in 29 cases, moderate density bands in 10 cases, and low density bands in 11 cases (Table: 4, and figure: 1). The third primer pairing probability (Pc) recorded the lowest incidence of high density bands among all the studied probabilities, as it possessed high density bands in 16 cases, moderate density bands in 15 cases, and low density bands in 19 cases, as illustrated in table (4), and figure (1). The fourth primer pairing probability (Pd) recorded low density bands in 13 cases, moderate density bands in 13 cases, and high density bands in 24 cases (Table 4 and figure 1). As an evaluation for the used primer pairing probabilities, there were 200 different PCR-product analysis records in the present study (4 probabilities for each one of the studied 50 cases); this resulted in a positive amplification of the target fungal chitin synthase conserved gene region for all the tested samples with variable concentrations of the produced DNA-amplification products. Consequently, high density bands were represented in 93 lanes (= 46.5% out of all tests), followed by low density bands (58 lanes = 29% out of all tests), then moderate density bands were presented in only 49 lanes (= 24.5% out of all tests). Table (4) also reveals that the second primer pairing probability (Pb) recorded the highest incidence of high density bands (29 tests) among all tested probabilities, followed by equal presentation for Pa, and Pd (24 tests for each), and the lowest incidence was recorded for Pc (16 tests). Accordingly, Pb was considered to be the most efficient primer pairing probability, producing high concentration of amplified DNA, and consequently good visualization of target fungal DNA fragments under different conditions of the unknown samples.

In conclusion, specific detection of fungal DNA in unknown corneal ulcer scrapings with specific chitin synthase gene primers was found to be a time-saving, reliable, and accurate strategy for early diagnosis of mycotic keratitis, in comparison to the ordinary culture techniques, specially by using the second primer pairing probability (Pb = P-1 + P-4 = forward primer: 5'- TAC AAG CTT ACT ATG TAT AAT GAG GAT -3' + reverse primer: 5'- TTA CTC GAG CTT ATA CTC AAA ATT TTG -3'), giving the highest incidence of high density bands among all the tested probabilities through the SCAR-PCR strategy, adopted in the present work.

In the last decade, many trials were adopted to use recent PCR-dependent techniques in the detection, and identification of fungal genome, isolated from different infected samples of various human body organs. This strategy was found to be more promising, rapid, and accurate presentation of fungal DNA, by using specific, or non specific primers throughout widely variable PCR techniques. Hay, and Jones (2010) evaluated these new molecular tools in the rapid detection, and correct diagnosis of superficial fungal infections, by comparing the time consumption of ordinary cultures (more than 14 days), and rapid identification of dermatophytosis causative fungi, and vaginal *Candida* infections by a new real-time PCR-based technique. Another study was adopted to evaluate the rapid detection of *Aspergillus* infections of human respiratory system, by development of RFLP-PCR-based strategy, in which more effective early treatment was very helpful in the healing of low-populated lung aspergillosis (Diba *et al.*, 2008).

A new diagnostic trial in India adopted 16S rRNA-based PCR technique for detection, and identification of different filamentous fungi, causing mycotic keratitis, representing positive results for 103 cases out of 114 cases under interest during the survey of Joseph *et al.* (2006). The development of oligonucleotide

microarray method to identify the clinical pathogenic fungi, isolated from different human fungal infection origins, succeeded to establish different 8 fungal genera, with genetically distinguished 122 strains of fungal pathogens (Huang *et al.*, 2006). O'Donnell *et al.* (2009) evaluated the efficacy of clinical signs examination, histopathology findings, culture results, and new adopted two-locus DNA sequence data base; and elucidated the higher efficacy of DNA-dependent strategy in the finger printing, and successful identification of *Fusarium* strains isolated from different human infections.

More recent comparative study was carried out by Vemuganti, *et al.* (2011) to evaluate the histopathological, and molecular diagnosis in a rapid, and accurate detection of corneal infections, recording positive fungal DNA visualization by the newly used PCR techniques in 89% of cases, compared with only 67% of cases for fungal elements visualized by histopathological staining of the collected samples. In the mean time, documents of ordinary cultures gave positive fungal growth only in 32% of studied microbial keratitis with delayed investigation rate; while a pan-fungal primers – based PCR technique increased the detection rate of fungal elements in 73% of causes with more rapid investigation (Kim, *et al.*, 2008). As a new strategy to control the more increasing rates of fungal keratitis, and more increasing rates of accompanying complications, mainly due to the delaying detection of fungal elements in the tested samples, a new strategy for rapid, and accurate detection of fungal keratitis was recently adopted in USA by Sixto, *et al.* (2012), depending on more specific primers, targeting more distinct fungal genome fragments, namely ergosterol metabolism-responsible genes in a real-time PCR strategy.

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Table 1. Fungi isolated from mycotic corneal ulcers during the year of survey (1/2008 – 12/2008):

Isolated fungal species	No. of isolate cases	Percentage out of total mycotic ulcer isolate cases	Time for first growth appearance on culture plates
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> var. <i>flavus</i> (Link, 1809)	19	38	4
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> (Tiegh, 1867)	12	24	4
<i>Penicillium lanosum</i> (Westling, 1911)	9	18	9
<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i> var. <i>moniliforme</i> (Sheld, 1904)	6	12	9
<i>Mucor fuscus</i> (Bainier, 1903)	2	4	4
<i>Cladosporium sphaerospermum</i> (Penz, 1882)	2	4	14
Total	50	100	4-14

Table 2. Efficiency of fungal detection in ordinary cultures, and adopted SCAR-PCR-product banding techniques:

Technique	Source of sample				Time to reveal results (days)
	Tap water	Standard bacterial sample	Standard fungal sample	Unknown samples (infected eye scraps)	
Fungal growth on culture	-ve	-ve	+ve	+ve	4-14
No. of bands in PCR product analysis	0	0	1	1	1
Size of revealed band (bp)	0	0	≈ 400	≈ 380 → 420	-

Table 3. Survey of band density for different primer pairing probabilities in SCAR-PCR-product visualization of fungal genome in mycotic corneal ulcers during the present study:

Case no.	P _a	P _b	P _c	P _d	Average band size (bp)
1	++	+++	++	++	420
2	+++	+++	++	+++	380
3	++	++	+	++	380
4	++	++	++	++	400
5	++	++	+	+	380
6	+	+	+	+	400
7	+	+	+	+	380
8	+++	+++	+	++	420
9	++	++	++	++	400
10	++	++	++	++	380
11	++	+++	+++	+++	380
12	+++	+++	+++	+++	400
13	+++	+++	+++	+++	380
14	+++	+++	+	+++	400
15	++	++	+++	+++	400
16	+++	+++	+	+	380
17	+	+++	+++	+++	400
18	+++	+++	+++	+++	380
19	+++	+++	+++	+++	380
20	+	+	+	+	400
21	+	+	+	+	400
22	+++	+++	+	+++	400
23	+++	+++	+++	+++	400
24	+++	++	++	+++	400
25	++	++	++	+++	400
26	+++	+++	+++	+	400
27	+	+	+	+	400
28	+	+++	+++	+++	420
29	+++	++	+++	++	420
30	+++	+++	++	++	420
31	+	+++	+++	+++	420
32	+++	+++	+	+	420
33	+++	+++	++	+++	420
34	+++	+++	+	+	420
35	+	+	+	+++	400
36	++	+++	++	+	400
37	+	+++	+	+++	400
38	+	+	++	+	400
39	+++	+	+	+++	400
40	+	+	+	+++	420
41	+++	+++	+++	+++	400
42	+++	+++	++	++	420
43	+++	+++	+++	+++	400
44	+	+	+	++	400
45	+++	++	+++	+++	380
46	+	+++	+++	+++	380
47	+++	+++	++	+	380
48	+++	+++	++	++	400
49	+	+++	++	++	420
50	++	+	+	++	380

P_a, P_b, P_c, and P_d = different primer pairing probabilities for PCR.

+ = Low density band,

++ = Moderate density band,

+++ = High density band.

Table 4. Efficiency of different primer pairing probabilities in the detection of fungal genome in mycotic corneal ulcers during the present study:

Primer pairing probability	No. of cases with low density bands	No. of cases with moderate density bands	No. of cases with high density bands	Total cases
P _a (P-1 + P-3)	15	11	24	50
P _b (P-1 + P-4)	11	10	29	50
P _c (P-2 + P-3)	19	15	16	50
P _d (P-2 + P-4)	13	13	24	50
Total cases	58	49	93	200
% out of total cases	29	24.5	46.5	100

P_a, P_b, P_c, and P_d = different primer pairing probabilities for PCR.

P-1, P-2 = specific forward primers of fungal chitin synthase gene.

P-3, P-4 = specific reverse primers of fungal chitin synthase gene.

Figure (1): Agarose gel electrophoresis for PCR product analysis of different unknown genome samples from human corneal scrabs.

M= DNA marker (Standard 1000 bp DNA ladder), P_a, P_b, P_c, P_d= Different primer pairing probabilities.

T= tap water sample, B= standard bacterial sample, F= standard fungal sample, Cases 1-50= unknown corneal scrabs.

المخلص العربى:

لقد صممت الدراسة الحالية بصفة أساسية لتحقيق الكشف السريع للقرحة الفطرية لقرنية الإنسان، حيث لوحظ أن زراعة المسحات من العدوى بالطريقة التقليدية مستهلكة للوقت. وقد استخدم زوج من البادئات المتخصصة في التعرف على الترتيب الجينى المسئول عن إنتاج إنزيم تخليق الكايتين - والمتوقع تواجده في كل عينات القرنية المصابة بالقرحة الفطرية - في تفاعل البلمرة المتسلسل لمضاعفة الحمض النووى. أكدت النتائج أن الطريقة المستخدمة كانت أكثر دقة، أكثر توفيراً للوقت، حيث تم الكشف عن الجينوم الفطرى خلال يوم عمل واحد فقط، بينما استغرقت المزارع التقليدية من 4 إلى 14 يوم لكشف عن النمو الفطرى.